

LANGUAGE EDUCATION: GOALS OF TEACHING FOREIGN LANGUAGE IN EDUCATIONAL ESTABLISHMENTS

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Abstract : The main goal of this research is to examine how interactive technologies can be used to teach foreign languages in higher education settings. Through our study, we discovered that using such technologies can positively impact students' ability to communicate and develop personal skills. As a result, we concluded that incorporating interactive techniques into the learning process is crucial for effective language education.

Keywords: a global language, education, English, communication, international standards, communication, language skills, educational institutions.

Introduction

One of the current challenges is to instill a sense of love and devotion towards the nation, a strong national pride, high morals, and spirituality, and enhance awareness of our rich heritage and universal values in the younger generation through foreign language education. Radical changes in the global education system are focused on creating optimal conditions for students to achieve mastery in foreign languages, enabling them to communicate effectively across different domains, and cultivate their oral and written proficiency in foreign languages. International organizations like UNESCO, UNICEF, the European University Association, and the European Network for Higher Education Quality are actively involved in developing students' capacity to think in foreign languages, communicate fluently, construct their intellectual abilities, and gauge their preparedness. The development of these matters as part of a broad agenda serves a vital role in shaping young learners' language skills and boosting their creative abilities through solving contemporary educational problems.

The education system in the Republic is undergoing a reform. To improve the system of higher education, coordination of curricula based on international standards has become essential, with a focus on foreign experience. The reform aims to improve the quality of education in Uzbekistan, considering national traditions and the mentality of the people. The Action Strategy for the development of the Republic highlights the importance of improving the quality and efficiency of higher education institutions based on international standards and encouraging innovative activities. This involves establishing partnerships with other leading scientific institutions, enhancing creative abilities, providing quality foreign language education, and improving the quality of training. The ability to read and comprehend original literature in a foreign language and communicate effectively on a given topic is deemed necessary. Therefore, classes are held in the higher education system to help future personnel acquire these skills. Learning foreign languages has become an essential requirement in today's globalized world.

In our country, teaching foreign languages is given special attention thanks to our independence. Many foreign language teachers have been trained, professional development opportunities have been created both at home and abroad, multimedia textbooks in English, German, and French have been developed, and electronic resources for learning English have been prepared. The establishment of language rooms is a clear indication of this effort. The primary objective is to provide young people with the opportunity to benefit from global civilization and information resources, and to promote international cooperation and communication by educating the younger generation in foreign languages and training professionals who are proficient in these languages. As the famous German scientist Y.V. As von Goethe once said, "He who does not know a foreign language does not know his own language." Therefore, it is crucial for not only foreign language experts but also for future graduates of non-language universities to learn foreign languages and communicate effectively. A proverb among our people suggests that "He who knows the language knows the culture." In fact, anyone who knows a foreign language will have numerous opportunities and advantages. Having a good command of foreign languages is now one of the main requirements for any job position. To emphasize the education system's importance, it's vital to prioritize the training of specialists from various fields. This includes the introduction of new technologies and techniques for learning foreign languages since language is crucial for communication, cultural and spiritual exchange between nations.

Conclusion

To summarize, it can be argued that practical objectives, educational goals, and cultural aspirations are closely interconnected and cannot be separated. In fact, the primary emphasis is placed on practical objectives since the attainment of the other goals can only be accomplished by mastering the foreign language in a practical context.

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